
Research

Experiences of Teachers Using Play-Based Learning Strategies and Instructional Techniques in Kindergarten

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Abstract: One of the new goals, purposes, and objectives that the kindergarten program brought was a pedagogical approach known as "Play-Based Learning" (PBL). Play-based learning (PBL) is a child-centered method that prioritizes curriculum information. Although the game offers advantages, it also has drawbacks. This innovative method employs evaluation strategies that place an emphasis on the need for time to establish a playing environment as well as curriculum requirements. The purpose of this qualitative research study was to look into the pedagogical strategies teachers in FDK use to promote play-based learning. In the study outlined below, two teachers were questioned using semi-structured interviews. This qualitative research study found that play-based learning may be taught using a variety of pedagogical methods. The engaged teachers also discussed issues and different teaching methods. The participating teachers also discussed challenges they faced and different approaches to integrating play-based learning. Some suggestions include having a firm understanding of play-based learning and providing educators with chances for professional growth.

Keywords: Full-Day Kindergarten, Pedagogical Techniques, Support, and Teacher Experiences

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Introduction

New visions, purposes, and objectives were introduced in 2010 with the replacement of The Kindergarten Program (2006) with the Full-Day Early Learning - Kindergarten Program (FDK) (Draft version). With our best future in mind: Implementing early learning in Ontario was a paper written by Charles Pascal in 2009, and FDK brought in new adjustments as a result. The purpose of Pascal's (2009) study was to guarantee a solid foundation for the early years, offer extended-day learning to children aged four and five, and ensure a smoother transition for kindergartners to grade one.

The new FDK program from the Ontario Ministry of Education incorporated these modifications and visions. The new FDK program also made use of the Play-Based Learning (PBL) educational strategy that was discussed in Pascal's study. In most classrooms, using play as a play based learning in the primary grades has all but disappeared. There is a ton of data supporting the advantages of play for kids from infancy to age eight (Jay & Knauss, 2018; Nolan & Paatsch, 2018). And one element of developmentally appropriate practice play (Copple & Bredekamp, 2009). According to a report from the American Academy of Pediatrics that Miller and Almon (2009) evaluated, play is essential to children's development because it helps them to develop their imagination, creativity, physical prowess, social and emotional intelligence, and cognitive abilities. The learning objectives for kindergarten have replaced what was once called first and second-grade expectations. The school day no longer includes play, a significant stress reducer (Miller & Almon, 2009). PBL is described in the curriculum paper as a kid-centered approach where kids participate in and learn via play (OME, 2010). Play and learning have strong connections in terms of numeracy, literacy, and social, physical, and emotional development because it helps kids to explore their surroundings and build knowledge (OME, 2010). Along with supporting experiential learning, play teaches pupils problem-solving techniques with strong linkages to real-world situations (Samuelsson & Johansson, 2006; Pyle & Bigelow, 2015). Although learning through play can have a significant impact on young children's learning, there are issues with this new approach, including assessment strategies (Karia, 2014; Pelletier, 2014; Martlew, Stephen, & Ellis, 2011), balancing play with teaching curriculum expectations (Bennett et al., 1997; Pyle & Bigelow, 2015), and a lack of time to set up the environment for play (Van Oers & Duijkers, 2013; Karia, 2014; Bennett et al., 1997) Despite these worries, not much is known about how to resolve them.

Significance of the Study

The advantages of play-based learning (PBL) experiences for kids in early childhood classrooms have been extensively researched (Fiorelli & Russ, 2012; Nitecki & Chung, 2013; Roskos & Christie, 2011; Weisberg et al., 2013). Studies have also shown that there is frequently a discrepancy between what research identifies as best practice and what occurs in classrooms (Bulunuz, 2013; Hatcher et al., 2012). The availability of play-based learning opportunities in schools has been impacted by increased academic requirements for young children, a topic that has been the focus of much research, but this study brought new views on the issue (De Hann et al., 2014; Lynch, 2014; Nitecki & Chung, 2013). Based on a better understanding of how instructors described their experiences with play-based learning in their classrooms, this study gave an understanding of why those gaps may emerge.

Because it shed light on the experiences of teachers in making decisions about how to instruct their students, this study was practically significant. This study may aid educational authorities in figuring out how to support teachers more effectively when they examine closely how kindergarten classrooms operate. Understanding why some strategies are used in classrooms and why others may not be may be useful to educational leaders.

The majority of research so far has been on the advantages for students, but little has been done to address the experiences of teachers. Because it filled a research gap, this work has empirical significance. Based on the experiences of the kindergarten teachers, this research helped draw linkages between what occurs in classrooms and potential causes. Theoretically, this study was significant since it expanded upon the relevance and application of theories previously put forward by Froebel (1896) and Vygotsky (1978)

Literature Review

The subject of play based learning (PBL) in kindergarten school was covered in a number of articles. While there is a wealth of material on the benefits of play for curriculum and instruction delivery in the preschool years, there is far less knowledge regarding using play to teach children in kindergarten through grade two, especially when high academic requirements are also expected to be reached (Nolan & Paatsch, 2018). The amount of play in primary schools has decreased with the introduction of strict academic standards, despite research showing that play is helpful for pupils in kindergarten through grade two (Bowdon, 2015; Miller & Almon, 2009).

Play-based learning is still challenging to successfully implement, even when schools have gone so far as to make it mandatory. This is due to a number of factors, including a lack of agreement on what play is (Miller & Almon, 2009; Pyle & Alaca, 2018;

Pyle & Danniels, 2017; Wallerstedt & Pramling, 2012), high standards for accountability and student achievement (Miller & Almon, 2009, Pyle & Danniels, 2017; Taylor & Boyer, 2020), a lack of training for teachers in play-based learning and child development (Brown, 2017; Fowler, 2016; Jay & Knaus, 2018; Walsh et al., 2010), and teacher identity concerns among peers (Nolan & Paatsch, 2018).

The introduction of play-based learning (PBL) in FDK classrooms sparked a lot of interest and excitement, but its execution caused instructors to feel uncomfortable and frustrated (Karia, 2014). Therefore, the goal of this literature review is to gather knowledge about the experiences and pedagogical techniques that instructors employ to introduce play-based learning. Since FDK is still a relatively new program, it's critical to discover how teachers are finding it and what teaching methods might be employed to help them feel less frustrated. The reasoning behind play-based learning and its significance for student development will also be examined in this review of the literature. Additionally, both good and negative teacher experiences with play-based learning will be further investigated. Finally, the study team will examine possible teaching strategies that are currently being used by professors in PBL settings.

During the literature research, several themes of information were related to the usage of Experiences of instructors employing play-based learning strategies and instructional techniques in kindergarten. Full-day kindergarten with play-based learning, play-based learning in the classroom: teacher perspectives, including positive encounters, issues; play-based learning teaching techniques, including fundamental tactics, techniques used by kindergarten instructors, and methods for play-based learning that are based on research for the successful implementation of play and play-based learning in the kindergarten.

The goal of this study was to learn more about the pedagogical techniques teachers in China Zhejiang Nanxun Hongda Kindergarten Affiliated with SISU FDK are employing to integrate play-based learning in their classrooms. Regarding play-based learning, teachers have identified both advantages and drawbacks. Teachers demonstrated an awareness of their roles, the benefits of play-based learning for inclusion, and classroom organization (Van Oers & Duijkers, 2013; Martlew et al., 2011; Karia, 2014; Bennett et al., 1997; Pyle & Bigelow, 2015). However, they also mentioned that play-based learning had problems with time management, assessment challenges, understanding play, and balancing teacher and student-directed learning (Van Oers & Duijkers, 2013; Karia, 2014; Bennett et al., 1997; Martlew et al., 2011; Pyle & Bigelow, 2015; Baker, 2014; Samuelsson & Johansson, 2006; McInnes, Howard, Miles, & Crowley, 2011; Walsh, McGuinness, Sproule, & Trew, 2010).

Teachers have implemented the previously mentioned strategies, such as differentiated instruction, adopting a different curriculum philosophy to teach play-based learning, observations, documentation, and workshops, in their classrooms in order to address some of the issues (Grant, Hindman, & Stronge, 2010; Bennett et al., 1997; OME, 2010; Brown, 2010; Jones et al., 2010). Although certain tactics for supporting play-based learning have been published, most of the research and recommendations originate from international studies. The methods' other drawback is that it's unclear how long they can be employed in the classroom.

Knowing whether the teachers who employed these tactics did so for a limited amount of time or for the entire academic year would be helpful. Additionally, there isn't enough proof to support the effectiveness of several of the general and teacher-used tactics stated in the list. It is important to take into account how these international teaching methods will work in a Chinese classroom even though they are good examples of play-based teaching. The goal of this study was to gain a deeper understanding of the methods that instructors at Zhejiang Nanxun Hongda Kindergarten employ to encourage play-based learning in FDK classrooms.

Research Methodology

An approach to qualitative research was applied in this study. The Zhejiang Nanxun Hongda Kindergarten (ZNHK) teachers were interviewed in semi-structured interviews for the study. According to Creswell (2013), qualitative research is a method of inquiry that starts out with a broad premise and an interpretive or theoretical lens to examine a study issue. Understanding and interpreting the results of qualitative research is important because it tackles concerns about social or human problems (Creswell, 2013; Fossey, Harvery, McDermott, & Davidson, 2002).

To do this, qualitative research describes and explains participants' interactions and experiences in a natural setting, such as the environment in which the issue has arisen (Creswell, 2013; Fossey et al., 2002). According to Creswell, the purpose of qualitative research is to highlight participant perspectives, promote self-reflection, and identify areas in which change is necessary. Many academics engage in qualitative research to better grasp a problem and acquire an understanding of people's actual experiences (Creswell, 2013).

A qualitative approach is required to address the study topic. Creswell (2013) and Patton (2013) both endorse the study's use of a qualitative research design (2002). In qualitative research, the purpose statement and the study questions are stated to maximize the opportunity for participant learning (p. 17). Due to the nature of the research topic and objective, qualitative research offered a real-world perspective on teachers' PBL experiences, problems, and solutions. This study documented the PBL experiences and instructional strategies of teachers.

Participants

Turner (2010) asserts that it's critical to pick the right candidates for interviews. Researchers must use sampling techniques like criteria and methods to give participant information in order to choose these suitable candidates (Turner, 2010).

Sampling requirements

The participants were chosen based on the following standards:

1. Teachers who have worked in kindergarten classrooms for at least a year
2. Educators that worked at Zhejiang Nanxun Hongda Kindergarten (ZNHK)
3. Teachers needed to comprehend play-based learning
4. Teachers were required to demonstrate some understanding of teaching techniques and the effects of play-based learning on student growth.

The teachers were required to have at least a year's worth of experience teaching in a kindergarten classroom in order to address the main study issue. This was done to make sure that teachers were aware of the advantages and issues of PBL as well as the methodology itself. Since the researcher was interested in finding out what teachers in this school board were doing and what their teaching practices were, teachers also needed to cooperate within the ZNHK. Teachers were also expected to be knowledgeable about different PBL teaching methods and how they affect students' growth. This would explain and serve as a manual for new teachers on how to instruct this innovative learning strategy.

Research Findings

In this chapter, the researcher reports and discusses the findings of four interviews with elementary school instructors at China Zhejiang Nanxun Hongda Kindergarten. To protect their identities, the participants will be identified as cocoa, Linda, Alisa, and Cat. The data gathered from the four interviews supplied the researcher with rich information that assisted in answering the main study question: What pedagogical techniques do teachers in FDK use to facilitate play-based learning? To answer the research topic, the researcher divided the data into three major themes (followed by multiple sub-themes):

1. Full-day kindergarten teacher's awareness of play-based learning,
2. Strategies for promoting play-based learning in full-day kindergarten,
3. Issues/Concerns regarding play-based learning in full-day kindergarten.

Analyzing the information from the interview with Chocolate and Cat, two elementary school teachers in Nanxun, revealed three themes. The main themes, which are followed by a number of sub themes, are:

1. Full-day kindergarten teacher's awareness of play-based learning,
2. Strategies for promoting play-based learning in full-day kindergarten,
3. Issues/Concerns regarding play-based learning in full-day kindergarten.

Knowledge of play-based education among teachers and the significance of discussing teachers' roles in the classroom and how they interpret play-based learning. Both teachers discussed how they believed that play-based learning was a means for students to build their knowledge, and how centers and hands-on resources supported student queries. Regarding their function as teachers in the classroom, the participants, however, had contrasting opinions. As a teacher, Chocolate thought it was her responsibility to direct students' learning and use specific teaching techniques. Cat, however, understood the value of working together with the children to support their questions and learn alongside them. Teachers can incorporate many teaching philosophies in their classrooms since play-based learning is open to interpretation. Because STEAM is connected to various curriculum strands, Chocolate claimed that it was an excellent teaching strategy to implement in her classroom. Cat, on the other hand, did not employ an instructional strategy but rather leveraged her students' passions to teach them essential abilities. The use of mindfulness in the classroom to encourage good self-regulation abilities is another teaching method that has come to light. When Cat acted out various scenarios, it was eye-opening to watch Chocolate instruct her students using props and yoga poses. What was significant was that both of these mindfulness techniques shared the desire to be self-sufficient tools for students to employ. Last but not least, the two participants discussed using observations as a tool for assessment. Despite the fact that they both used classroom observations to express themselves, their goals were different for each. Chocolate used the observations at the end of a unit to address specific needs, whereas Cat applied them right away. The participants used a variety of setup methods for their classrooms. While waiting for the pupils' inquiries to the surface, Chocolate sets up her centers by giving them the necessary resources. Cat, on the other hand, creates her centers by bringing together the interests of her students. The two participants also talked about planning. Unlike Cat, Chocolate thought that planning was a crucial component of play-based learning. Cat realized that students' interests fluctuate a lot, so she doesn't make detailed plans.

Teachers require the right kind of support in order to successfully encourage a play-based learning environment. Several play-based classrooms, according to Chocolate, frequently don't have a uniform appearance. She frequently questioned if she was adhering to play-based learning standards. Cat, on the other hand, thought that the choice of how to organize a classroom should be left to the instructor. The lack of support for offering instructors resources was the next thing Chocolate noted. She was forced to buy the materials on her own due to a paucity of supplies. When it comes to bridging SK kids to Grade 1, Cat observed a dearth of help.

Concluding Remarks

Finding out the pedagogical techniques teachers in FDK are employing to support play-based learning was the aim of this study. This finding is significant for educators working in kindergarten classes since play is becoming increasingly recognized as a developmental activity. Play-based learning may be interpreted in many different ways, which has an impact on how teachers approach it in their classrooms, the researcher discovered via her research. In contrast to acting as a facilitator and co-teaching with students, modeling students' learning and using explicit teaching methods are both used. The paucity of teaching materials and mechanisms of support for play-based learning by instructors was another finding of the study. Many times, without assistance, teachers were required to look for instructional resources and aids on their own. The research did, however, offer important insights into the ways in which instructors are always refining their methods and ideologies in order to better serve their pupils.

Aside from administrators and ministries of education/school boards, recommendations were also made for instructors. These suggestions included giving professional development programs, producing fresh records that guarantee a precise definition, and giving suitable resources. Teachers could feel more assured thanks to this new approach, which would also improve their instructional strategies.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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